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Light Processing Unit

Sanat Mohanty

January 2026

Make the 7 logic gates on a CD by burning 0s and 1s to it and then put a LEDs high density laser above it where CD doesn't move but the laser light moves above it at light speed in high density laser LEDs. Read the Output. The advantages of such a system are:

it can process at light speed without ever overheating infinitely.

use ionosphere backscratching for short wave internet with exact equations of phase.

The details are classified under SIU.

References

- [1] Mohanty, S. (2025). *Cosmic Algorithm and Light Processor*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16945901>